

Comparative Mechanism of Quality Management in Higher Education Institutions

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Abstract: The article examines the history and economic directions of the leading international, national and profile assessment systems to improve the work on assessment systems in higher education institutions in the Republic of Azerbaijan. Parameters are defined to ensure compatibility in each direction. Requirements have been developed for high quality and frequency of citations of pedagogical / academic staff, payment processing and quality indicators in the labor market, reputation of equipment in the labor market, leadership in scientific research, increasing the value of research. The study of the work on the systematization of rankings, assessment, substantiation of the essence of the concepts by conducting theoretical generalizations, is one of the means of improving the quality of higher education. The forthcoming tasks for the higher education system in the Republic of Azerbaijan, the formation and improvement of scientifically based methodology, taking into account the current state of higher education, the problem of determining the achievements of world experience in assessing and building the quality of higher education are solved and analyzed at the pedagogical level.

Introduction.

The ranking of higher education institutions was first implemented by organizations and institutions in 2003. Different criteria - the number of scientific publications of higher education institutions, academic mobility, quality of pedagogical / academic staff, frequency of citations to works, quality indicators of payments in the labor and labor market, reputation in the labor market, leadership in research production, high level of research, -index A rating table is prepared for the evaluation of contributions to science, internet governance and other parameters. To evaluate the leading universities, various - global, international rating systems and some existing universities are trying to implement national evaluation mechanisms from those represented in the

international rating systems. In 2003, the Center for World-class Universities of the Institute of Higher Education of Shanghai Jiao Tong University was ranked and updated annually by the Academic Ranking of World Universities - ARWU. Webmetric Ranking of World Universities), Times Higher Education - QS World University Rankings (THE-QS), a joint project of Quacquarelli Symonds and TSL Education Ltd of the United Kingdom in 2004, and the Government of Taiwan in 2007. It is possible to study a number of authoritative international systems, such as the Performance Ranking of Scientific Papers for World Universities.

In many countries around the world (Argentina, Australia, Brazil, Chile, Pakistan, Ukraine, etc.), the first economy is the study of Canadian websites in foreign languages, university research results on websites, non-publication of articles on behalf of educational institutions in academic databases, etc. Separate national ratings (systems) have been developed due to their inability to be included in international rankings.

He has been working with the Russian Ministry of Education from the CIS (the process is carried out by the Patani Charitable Society) since 2004, and since 2006 he has been managing higher education institutions.

The process of determining the ranking of higher education institutions in the Republic of Azerbaijan was organized by the order of the Minister of Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated 11 2013, No. 842. was started as one of the winning projects of the participants. The main documents on the current problem are the documents submitted by the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on October 24, 2013 in accordance with the strategic goals of the "State Strategy for the Development of Education in the Republic of Azerbaijan". The executor of the project was the Organization of Specialists Educated Abroad (AKTAM). "Determination of the ranking of universities in the Republic of Azerbaijan" A proposal has been prepared in the field of developing a national governance mechanism to achieve the appointment of Azerbaijani universities in international systems.

It is necessary to take more agile steps in the field of reconstruction of higher education institutions in Azerbaijan, the development of a national evaluation mechanism, the appointment of more in the international evaluation system against the background of the world scientific and labor market.

The main reasons for the research are:

- Study of the work on the economicization of higher education institutions (history and strategic directions of the leading international, national and profile rating systems);
- To set requirements for the quality and frequency of citations of pedagogical / academic staff, quality indicators of calculations in the labor and labor market and the reputation formed in the labor market, the percentage of admission to traditional research, industry leadership in scientific research, increasing the value of research.

Object of research. These are international, national and profile evaluation mechanisms of higher education institutions.

Subject of research. International, national and profile rating systems of higher education institutions and the definition of parameters to ensure compliance in each area.

Scientific novelty of the research. The study of the work on the systematization of rankings, assessment, substantiation of the essence of the concepts by conducting theoretical generalizations, is one of the means of improving the quality of higher education. The forthcoming tasks for the higher education system in the Republic of Azerbaijan, the problem of determining the achievements of the use of world experience in the field of formation, improvement of scientifically based methodology, assessment and establishment of the quality of higher education, taking into account the current state of higher education are analyzed at the pedagogical level. has been.

Leading international (QS, Times Higher Education, ARWU-Shanghai rating, Forbes), national and profile rating systems of higher education institutions

The development of the higher system creates a general picture of the quality of life of the socio-economic situation. Measuring the level and quality of development means referring to these international and national standards to monitor and improve outcomes.

The different assessment systems and rankings available during the establishment of higher education institutions are not considered to be as objective as they are. The reason is that the indicators and achievements of higher education institutions have different qualities, depending on the ability to express themselves only in numbers. In order to determine the main criteria for the application of common standards for different assessment systems, the UNESCO Higher Education Center has developed the Berlin Principles from 16 articles on the appointment of international experts . 13 Medicine, engineering, mathematics, architecture, etc. The principles of evaluation of scientific publications are included, despite the fact that each higher education institution profiled by field has different needs, pedagogical / academic staff and student profiles.

Specific data in the database obtained as a result of measuring quality, overall performance, and expressions with numbers that are considered reliable are possible. therefore, each higher education institution can adjust its mission and vision to international and national assessment systems so that it can integrate into the content of education in international practice. The most well-known rating systems in international practice are THE - QS, ARWU-Shanghai rating and others.

QS International University Rankings has been ranked since 2004 based on Quacquarelli Symonds and different academic criteria. QS determines the ranking of universities by evaluating them according to different criteria

¹²UNESCO European Center for Higher Education (UNESCO-CEPES)

¹³ HEI Ratings - Berlin Principles on Ranking of Higher Education Institutions. (Berlin, May 18-20, 2006) http://ireg-observatory.org/en_old/berlin-principles

(including specialties and faculties), each of which has a maximum of 100 points from 4 main factors (Table 1.1.1.):

Table 1.1.1. Calculation of results on QS International University Rankings.

Amil	Criterion	drawings	Significance
Quality of scientific research	Judge / expert opinion	Total score based on the judge's opinion	40%
	Works quoted by pedagogical / academic staff	Ratio of pedagogical issues in the governing bodies of the university	20%
Job opportunities for graduates	Opinion and attitude of employers	Employee relationship survey results	10%
with international	foreign teacher	Number of foreign teachers working at the university	5%
	foreign student	Number of students studying at the university	5%
Quality education	teachers and students	Number ratio between teacher and student	20%

ARWU-Shanghai Ranking - The Ranking Council at Shanghai Jiaotong University has been compiling a ranking of the world's top 500 universities every year since 2003. Shanghai University, which developed the first ranking of the company, initially set a goal to conduct a program between Chinese universities and the world's leading universities. ARWU Shanghai's rating has risen to the level of this most appreciated structure due to its agile and accurate calculation and measurement based on design and evaluation (Table 1.1.2.).

Table 1.1.2. Calculation of results on ARWU-Shanghai rating.

Amil	Criterion	Code	Significance
Quality education	Number of pedagogical / academic Nobel Prize winners	Retired	10%
Job opportunities for graduates	Number of pedagogical / aka winners in the field of research	Reward	20%
	The latest pedagogical / academic number quoted in 21 sections / fields	HiCi	20%
Research opportunities / tools	Articles published in the journal Nature and Science *	N&S	20%
	Science Citation Index-Expanded,	SCI	20%

	Social Science Citation Index 'published articles		
The size of the university	The performance of universities in terms of size - infrastructure	Great	10%
Total			100%

There are other authoritative systems that prepare different levels of higher education institutions:

Newsweek Magazine's Top 100 Universities in the World (Top 100 Global Universities);

Webometrics: Cybermetric Laboratories. World University Rankings (Webometrics: World Universities' Ranking on the Web);

Google Search - International University Rankings (G-Factor International University Rankings);

MINES - International Ranking of World Universities;

HEETACT - Taiwan Higher Education Evaluation and Accreditation Council International University Scientific Research Performers Ranking (Performance Ranking of Scientific Articles for World Universities);

Leiden - a rating prepared by The Center for Science and Technology Studies at the University of Leiden in the Netherlands ;

SCImago rating - a collaborative competition system developed by SCImago, using a Scopus database of 1700 journals;

China Wuhan University Global University Rating (Global University Ranking) and so on.

Activity of websites of higher education institutions in the Republic of Azerbaijan meeting international requirements, availability of scientific results, availability of publication of articles in impact factor journals, students, teachers, etc. with foreign universities. The establishment of a national assessment is a great help in strengthening such institutions. For this purpose, the inclusion of Azerbaijani higher education institutions in international rankings, as well as raising the rank of existing universities, etc. It is possible to achieve such advantages:

Pedagogical / academic staff

- the ratio of the number of professors to the number of students;
- according to the number of doctors of sciences;
- the ratio of the number of associate professors to the number of associates;
- the ratio of the number of PhDs to the number of doctors;
- the ratio of the number of non-scientific research and the number of non-scientific names to the number of students;
- the ratio of the number of teachers with foreign payments to the number of teachers;
- the ratio of the number of masters to the number of students;
- the ratio of the number of masters with foreign payments to the number of volumes

- the ratio of the number of doctoral students and dissertators to the number of students;
- size of the number of foreign documents and dissertations;
- the ratio of the number of foreign documents to the number of volumes.
- Scientific activity
- ratio of the number of published scientific articles to the number of pedagogical / academic staff;
- measurement of the number of scientific articles published abroad to the number of pedagogical / academic staff;
- the ratio of the number of scientific articles published in journals with an impact factor to the number of pedagogical / academic staff;
- the ratio of the number of monographs to the number of pedagogical / academic staff;
- the ratio of the number of textbooks and teaching aids to the number of pedagogical / academic staff;
- The ratio of the number of patents for inventions in Azerbaijan to the number of pedagogical / academic staff;
- the ratio of the number of patents for foreign inventions to the number of pedagogical / academic staff;
- h-indexes of pedagogical / academic staff on profiles.
- university website
- external references to university websites (number of citations provided);
- the number of valuable files posted on the university website;
- the number of sub-pages and directories of the university website;
- the quality of the university website.

In 2004, UNESCO's European Center for Higher Education and the Institute for Higher Education Policy (US) oversaw the International Expert Ranking Commission to ensure uniformity in the rankings. The general principles and standard methodology for determining higher education institutions based on the Berlin principle were presented to the staff. According to this principle, the rating of higher education institutions is selected independently of three independent:

- ranking of academic resources of higher education institutions, pedagogical / democratization of higher education institutions, significant achievements, teaching, material resources, security and other criteria;
- internal assessment of higher education institutions, ie teachers;
- Recruitment of criteria-based facilities within each unit, including evaluation by central and local executive authorities, large and small companies.

There are criteria to use everywhere. For example, classes on academic resources collect materials from universities on 7 criteria and 39 indicators. Then get a survey between each group of 7 higher education questionnaires, additional teachers and changes. At the same time, in order to determine the level of universities and the information that a private organization or enterprise has hired or recognized in recent years, information is generated, and the question of which university's equipment should be developed is raised. then,

the ranking of the university is obtained by the sum of the materials collected in the 3rd grade. Payment points by categories are determined in advance, resource identification, pedagogical / academic staff, high quality, paid and free education, ratio of foreign level, research potential of universities, proportionality and optimal costs of funding and income, enrollment and payment of students . results of the educational process, quality of technology, socio-cultural life, etc. Evaluation by criteria - measurements.

Quality of pedagogical / academic staff (Nobel, Fields, etc.) and frequency of citations to their works

In order to improve the quality of higher education, a number of studies are being conducted in connection with the establishment of international organizations to determine the rankings of universities.

Quality management mechanisms of higher education institutions are one of the tools to improve the quality of higher education. Technical issues for the higher education system in the Republic of Azerbaijan are the creation of a scientifically based methodology for obtaining the automotive status of higher education, the possibility of using world experience in assessing and developing the quality of higher education. The main function of rating is as follows:

providing information for decision-making (to the applicant and their creation; to politicians, employers, international organizations);

to stimulate the development of higher education institutions and assist in creating this development environment;

stimulate the establishment of internal quality improvement centers of higher education institutions and the establishment of centers.

The development of the ranking methodology should be based on the Berlin Principles for the Ranking of Higher Education Institutions (Berlin, May 2006) (Appendix 1).

First of all, important principles are taken in the higher education system of Azerbaijan:

the ability to accept the dependence of educational institutions and define their mission and functions (that is, the reserve difference between public and private educational institutions);

Accurate accounting and measurement of linguistic, cultural, economic and historical contexts in the higher education system in Azerbaijan Accurate accounting of relevant experience (the “quality” of a higher education institution is not treated in the same way in all installation or education systems);

use as much of the information used or verified as possible;

application of organizational rules that increase the security of departments;

Ensuring an accurate understanding of all the factors used in the rating, ratings.

The groups based on the purpose of making the (national) ranking of higher education institutions in the republic are:

Protection of information for the public (applicants and their management, politicians, international organizations, employment agencies) to make decisions;

To stimulate research among universities;

The establishment and scientific impetus for the improvement of internal quality improvement centers in higher education;

Corruption and coefficients of academic autonomy of higher education institutions during the educational process;

To stimulate the study of self-government in higher education and in the educational process.

In order to build a ranking of higher education institutions based on international experience, the quality indicators of complex activities should be selected independently of 3:

1. Academic resources of the higher education institution (education of students, achievements of the teaching staff, provision of teaching and financial resources);

2. Evaluation of teachers and assessment from within the higher education institution;

3. Evaluation of the country's development of the higher education institution, central and regional executive bodies, secondary and small organizations.

Assessment of the educational institution as one of the pedagogical factors / as one of the factors of the assigned Disability is measured by approximately close, common criteria all over the world. The criteria selected for the assessment of teaching / academic staff at the University of North Carolina in the United States are summarized in general centers:

1. Teaching, recommendations, curriculum, development orientation on education

a. scientific degree in the specialty;

b. lesson design;

c. lesson presentation, organization

d. student research management;

e. laboratory for assistants working in groups;

f. developmental steps related to curricula.

2. specialty research, creativity and professional activities.

a. scientific publications;

b. speeches at conferences;

c. and so on.

3. Service to university, work, media and profession.

a. benefits to university management

b. employment, media services;

c. service to the profession;

A portfolio is prepared for each job submitted, and based on the results obtained during the evaluation, it is decided to reassign, reward and work on a permanent basis.

Quality indicators of graduates in the labor and labor market (Nobel, Fileds) and the reputation formed in the labor market

In order to improve the quality of higher education, it is necessary to create a country to determine the rankings of universities, based on the criteria

for assessing the level of readiness of departments and organizations of individual ministries of higher education:

- assessment qualification, knowledge and assessment of business quality;
- preparation of a young specialist for an 8-hour working day;
- switch from one type of activity to another;
- gather a working group to help solve practical or current issues;
- give good performance and ideas;
- quality of fundamental and theoretical training.

Higher education institutions are grouped in the post-graduate period as socio-economic benefits, socio-economic benefits, individual economic benefits, individual social benefits (Table 1.3):

Table 1.3. Benefits of higher education in the post-education period socio-economic benefits, socio-social, individual economic benefits, social individual benefits supplements.

Socio-Economic Benefits	Social Benefit	Individual Economic Benefit	Individual Social Benefit
Increase in tax revenues	Decrease in the number of crimes	high standard of living	Better health and longevity
Increase in productivity	Growth in activities in the field of donations and social services	Easy access to the job market	Complete well-being for children / children - living conditions
Growth in consumption	Development of civic responsibility	Investment growth	Make healthier decisions as a customer
Increased adaptability	Social unity / equality	Better working conditions	Rising personal status
Exemption from the expected withholding of funds from the state	Development of skills to adapt and use technology	Individual / specialty mobility	More hobbies and leisure activities

European Statistics - EUROSTAT 14, Malta is the European country between the ages of 20-34 with the highest percentage of any higher education institution in the last three years, with a score of 96.7%. Iceland is in second place with 95.8%, followed by the Netherlands with 94.8%.

Depending on the university, the proportion of those employed for three years is 94.3% in Germany; 88.4% in the United Kingdom; Finland 88.3%;

¹⁴ European Statistical Office

84.4% in France; 77.9% in Spain; citizens 64.2%; It is 62.8% in Italy and 59.0% in Greece 15.

Leadership in the field of scientific research, the degree of importance of research (assessment of the results obtained on the H-index)

The concept of a research university was first formed in 1818 on the example of Humboldt University. The presence of 200 years of experience allows universities to meet the basic conditions of transformation into research, while maintaining differences in mission and vision.

It is clearly observed that research, research, scientific publications have a special weight in all research systems. In order for the higher education institutions of the Republic of Azerbaijan to be represented at a higher level, it is necessary to include serious, highly productive researchers in the staff, create the required conditions, and manage career goals. Any higher education institution earned by productive researchers receives the status of "research university, scientific institution" in its position:

- Involvement of pedagogical / academic staff with high research skills;
- creating additional time for pedagogical / academic research;
- providing the funding required for the research;
- building infrastructure for research development;
- Involvement of doctoral students, research assistants in the enterprise for the development of research;
- Supervision of scientific publications in the process of attestation and evaluation of pedagogical / academic staff.

The initial criteria for the evaluation of scientific research, scientific publications provide information on the scientific capacity of the publication, provided that it is more or less important:

publication - It is useful to use the total number of productivity. However, the validity of the publication is considered to be a very valid criterion for information knowledge about its usefulness.

The total number of iqs is a research, a quote to reveal the usefulness of the research (the number is a reasonable criterion).

The number of citations to each publication is the criterion that ensures that the first two criteria are evaluated together. The publication provides a significant amount of funding for the research of a young scientist who is just beginning his career with a very high number of publications and has a limited number of publications. Acquisition of a publication can result in an average annual time requirement of five researchers (due to the large number of publications in the denominator).

It is a criterion that publications with more / more citations of quality publications are important and worthy of attention (eg, publication with 5 citations).

H-indexsi was adopted in 2005 under the same name in honor of the required elmmetric designation of the American physicist Jorge Hirsch,

¹⁵ EUROSTAT - Gender, level of education and employment rates of young people who are not in education and training for years after graduating from the highest level of education

originally from Argentina. The H-index is a quantitative indicator of the activities of scientists (authors), or a group of scientists (groups of authors), as well as the activities of the science and educational institution they represent, according to scientific publications and publications.

The H-index can also be found in the scientific literature as a Hirsch index [16]. The h-index is widely used in the plan of measuring scientific productivity, and the professional reputation of a scientist (scientific unit) raises questions that help to give a limited impression, expressed only in single, numerical terms. However, the total number of publications is considered more useful than the systems in which the total number of citations to all publications and the number of citations to each publication are obtained separately. For example, authors who publish one (initial) article on a topic and continue it, or who can get 1-2 quotations from each event of several articles, can be fairly excluded from the ranking. This provides a struggle to get the maximum number of citations to each article, with the ability to publish more material to have a full h-index [17]:

$$h\text{-index} = n_a$$

10 references to an author's article are equal to 1 probable reference to each of his 10 articles, ie in both cases the author's h-index is equal to 1.

Formally, if we take the number of citations (functions) given to any publication, the h-index is calculated in the following order:

Once the value of f is from the largest to the smallest, it is necessary to make the final project that is greater than or equal to the level of f . We call this position h . For example, the h-index of an author who quotes 5 scientific publications A, B, C, D, E in turn, 10, 8, 5, 4 and 3, respectively, is equal to 4. Because the number of citations in the fourth edition is 4, in the fifth edition only 3 citations were received. However, in the sample where the same publications quoted 25, 8, 5, 3, 3, the h-index is 3, and the number of quotes from the difficult, fourth edition is 3.

$$f(A) = 10, f(B) = 8, f(C) = 5, f(D) = 4, f(E) = 3 \rightarrow h\text{-index} = 4$$

$$f(A) = 25, f(B) = 8, f(C) = 5, f(D) = 3, f(E) = 3 \rightarrow h\text{-index} = 3$$

If we sort from the largest value of the function f to the smallest value, we can calculate the h-index in the following order:

$$h\text{-index}(f) = \left\lfloor \max_{\{i\}} \left\{ \min(f(i), i) \right\} \right\rfloor$$

In the next example, the same condition can be represented by a simpler calculation method (calculation tree):

is provided automatically (systematically), including from the user profile in Google Scholar, "there is no need for manual calculation." [18]

➤ Against the background of the emerging creativity, the authors can achieve their own h-index in two ways: on their own initiative:

➤ to cite their works in new research [19];

¹⁶Locally referred to as the Hirsch index in the field of elmmetry in the CIS, this system is referred to in the international scientific community as the H-index.

¹⁷Each quote in an article also allows you to measure what opportunities can be useful for research with it.

¹⁸Google Scholar is a full-text search engine for scientific publications.

➤ by exceeding the gain without damaging the number of citations received by each gain, or the majority.

In the first case, the reasons allow the author to quote:

- bring the article or research to a more advanced level and update it;
- increase the availability of articles and research, and increase the frequency of encounters if a lower-rated journal quotes a more popular journal in the field;
- to ensure that research and scientific publications remain in the scientific literature;
- allow a new article or research to be read simply through advertising;
- recall articles or research that have little or no citation;
- to prove that he / she is a “professional”, “expert” in the field, to convince the reviewers (judges) who evaluate the articles and researches;
- proposed in the article and research, methodology, approach, method, tool, etc. to increase the relevance of the problem to provide examples that will substantiate and develop;
- raise your own quote apple as a figure.

In the latter case, even with a minimum number of citations, the increasing number of articles increases the likelihood of encountering articles by the same author more than other researchers. An increase in the h-index is possible because the increasing frequency of encounters, in turn, increases the chances of getting more citations.

In the international scientific environment, the state of the h-index in terms of the humanities and social sciences, as well as mathematics, is not considered completely successful. The obtained work creates serious differences between different sciences and disciplines. H-index, the identification and more accurate measurement of scientists using the unity of prestige of people from different disciplines, the ability to use the proposal as an optimal mechanism.

The result

Achieving scientific results in higher education institutions in the Republic of Azerbaijan, publication of articles in impact factor journals, special weight of research in higher education institutions, achieving the status of “research, scientific institution”, gathering students and teachers with foreign universities, activity of websites to meet international requirements, etc. . . It is possible to manage such institutions to achieve a position in national evaluation, and as a result to be successfully represented in international evaluation systems. For this purpose, the inclusion of Azerbaijani higher education institutions in international rankings, as well as raising the rank of existing universities, etc. it is possible to achieve such advantages.

Provides an opportunity to obtain and make suggestions in connection with the generalization of research materials:

One of the tools to improve the quality of higher education is the quality management mechanisms of higher education institutions. Technical issues for

¹⁹Self-citation - the author's research and efforts to continue creativity are considered useful, as the quote is not obtained in the general account.

the higher education system in the Republic of Azerbaijan are to determine the possibility of using world experience in the field of creation, improvement of scientific methodology, assessment of the quality and development of higher education by obtaining a car substantiation of higher education. The main function of rating is as follows:

providing information for decision-making (to the applicant and their creation; to politicians, employers, international organizations);

to stimulate the development of higher education institutions and assist in creating this development environment;

stimulate the establishment of internal quality improvement centers of higher education institutions and the establishment of centers.

Criteria for establishing a country to determine the level of higher education to improve the quality of higher education, assessment of the level of readiness of departments and organizations of individual ministries of higher education are considered expedient:

- assessment qualification, knowledge and assessment of business quality;
- preparation of a young specialist for an 8-hour working day;
- switch from one type of activity to another;
- gather a working group to help solve practical or current issues;
- give good performance and ideas;
- quality of fundamental and theoretical training.

It is clearly observed that research, research, scientific publications have a special weight in all research systems. In order to be represented at a higher level in the control systems of higher education institutions of the Republic of Azerbaijan, it is necessary to include serious, high-level, initially productive researchers, to provide the required conditions, to manage career goals. Any higher education institution where productive researchers are strong gains the status of "research, scientific institution":

- Involvement of pedagogical / academic staff with high research skills;
- creating additional time for pedagogical / academic research;
- providing the funding required for the research;
- building infrastructure for research development;
- Involvement of doctoral students, research assistants in the enterprise for research;

➤ Supervision of scientific publications in the process of attestation and evaluation of pedagogical / academic staff.

The widely used h-index of the scientific productivity measurement plan raises questions as well as giving a limited impression of the professional reputation of a scientist (scientific unit) limited to a single, numerical expression. However, only the total number of publications, the total number of citations to all publications, and the number of citations to each publication separately are considered more useful than the systems in which they are obtained. For example, issues allow authors to be fairly excluded from the rankings if they do not publish one (initial) article in the field and do not continue, or if each article of several articles can receive 1-2 quotations. This

provides a struggle to get the maximum number of citations to each article, with the ability to publish more material to have a full h-index.

Ratings serve to ensure quality in higher education, and in the ranked plans, it is possible to clearly see the location of each university and the current situation, problems, shortcomings, as well as advantages. The university should visit the internal industry strategy to take steps to improve the quality of education, the state, management, information and system according to the results of the assessment - to ensure the performance of the applicant / student.

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